

Consensus is Oligarchy, Consent is Liberty

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Abstract

Keywords:

1. Introduction

Worldfree's primary aim is to build a free and more effective business network using an advanced and stable asset-backed cryptocurrency, in a virtual world accessed through natural language (normally-spoken language, initially English, but later multi-language). The company's origin as a software developer with commercial software systems sold to many G200 companies for searching and delivering direct answers to questions from live, unstructured text is a value when brought to the cryptocurrency field. Yet, there are other pressing problems with the blockchain technology that preclude its use as a vehicle for introducing Worldfree's proprietary natural language reasoning technology. Chiefly, the blockchain is not a scalable technology, and the consensus method of decision-making often touted as an advantage, is in fact a disadvantage, as this White Paper discusses. There are better, more just, rational and equitable methods for decision making. The cryptocurrencies themselves suffer from economically poor design in general.

First among uses of currencies is as a medium of exchange. But as a consequence of their success, and early-stage design, today's currencies are massively deflationary, if not generally unstable. As they rise in price (as if successful equities), their purchasing power likewise increases. This is seemingly good for owners, and encourages holding cryptocurrencies, but not spending them. The crypto-economic world is thus stifled. Just as modern central bankers make great efforts to avoid deflationary environments because they stunt economies, a cryptocurrency must be designed to be a more functional alternative than fiat currencies, so that daily use for buying and selling other items is encouraged as a practical alternative currency for normal business needs. Worldfree's FreeMark is a new cryptocurrency to be introduced in 2018 that will eventually have 100% backing, automatically pegged by the Atomic Central Bank (®) to a basket of 20 commodities. It can be immediately converted into most other currencies or used to purchase goods and services on the Worldfree Network.

Holding it should deliver an increase in ownership on an average balance, correlated to the absolute value of the growth of the money supply. Thus it works contrary to normal fiat currencies, where increases in money supply reduce value; with the FreeMark they receive more of them at the same value. Worldfree also introduces Nodechain technology, which is different than a blockchain because it does not store transactions system-wide. It operates in

May 7, 2018

a massively parallel architecture, and file sizes per node are anticipated at less than 500kB, with a 20X redundancy factor, irrespective of the network's size .

Transactions on the Nodechain network can be processed predominantly on the participating parties' systems, with an effectively randomly-selected node updating the coin ownership, accessed through a function of a hash pointer. The patent-pending Nodechain still fulfils the design requirements to eliminate double spending, with greater security and better privacy, overcomes the limitations of the consensus paradigm, and processes transactions in seconds for each participant, irrespective of network size. It is distributed with redundancy, using extent-based parallel access. The Worldfree Network utilizes a cryptocurrency foundation engineered for prime-time and mass adoption, with a better designed economic and technological foundation.

Author biography

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May 7, 2018